

1 Title: Reforming Allied Health service provision in residential aged care
2 to improve the rehabilitation reach: a feasibility study

3

4 Abstract:

5 Aim: My Therapy is an allied health guided, co-designed rehabilitation self-management program for
6 residents of aged care facilities. This study aimed to determine the feasibility of implementing My
7 Therapy in the residential aged care setting.

8 Methods: This observational study was conducted on a 30-bed wing, within a 90-bed metropolitan
9 residential aged care facility, attached to a public health service, in Victoria, Australia. Staff and
10 resident data were collected prospectively over 6-weeks (staff focus groups, patient surveys, and
11 audits) to evaluate the feasibility domains of acceptability, reach and demand, practicality,
12 integration, limited efficacy testing, and adaptations.

13 Results: Twenty-six residents and five allied health staff (physiotherapy and occupational therapy)
14 participated. My Therapy was *acceptable* to residents (survey) and staff (focus groups). Via initial My
15 Therapy discussions between the resident and the therapists, to determine goals and resident
16 preferences, My Therapy reached 26 residents (n=26/26, 100% *program reach*), with 15 residents
17 subsequently receiving a rehabilitation program (n=15/26, 58% *program demand*). The remaining 11
18 residents didn't participate due to resident preference or safety issues (n=11/26, 42%). Collecting
19 physical function outcome measures for *limited efficacy testing* was *practical*, and the cost of My
20 Therapy was AUD\$6 per resident per day, suggesting financial *integration* may be possible. Several
21 *adaptations* were required, due to limited allied health staff, complex resident goal setting and
22 program co-design.

23 Conclusion: My Therapy has the potential to improve the rehabilitation reach of allied health services
24 in residential aged care. While introducing this low-cost intervention is feasible, adaptations were
25 required for successful implementation.

26 Key words: Aged Care, Allied Health, Empowering, Physical Activity, Self-management, Self-practice,
27 Co-design

28

29 Introduction:

30 In 2021, the Royal Commission into Aged Care Quality and Safety recommended a comprehensive
31 reform of the Australian aged care system¹. The recommendations stated that aged care should
32 “assist older people to live an active, self-determined and meaningful life” and that “care and
33 supports should, as far as possible, emphasise restoration and rehabilitation, with the aim of
34 maintaining or improving older people’s physical and cognitive capabilities and supporting their self-
35 determination”. For the allied health team in residential aged care services, this is key to reforming
36 how current scarce allied health services are delivered, to ensure services maximise resident
37 rehabilitation reach and impact.

38 Alongside nursing and medical care, allied health care is important in residential aged care to
39 optimise nutrition, oral health and communication, and minimise adverse events such as falls²⁻⁴. In
40 addition, allied health services can increase resident's physical activity and function through
41 rehabilitation, resulting in short and long term positive impacts on resident's independence, health
42 and wellbeing³⁻⁷.

43 My Therapy is an allied health-guided self-management program that has been designed to: (i)
44 empower residents to participate in meaningful, individually tailored co-designed rehabilitation self-
45 management programs to increase daily physical activity and independence through self-practice,
46 and (ii) improve the rehabilitation reach of allied health. To date, My Therapy has been successfully
47 implemented in the adult inpatient rehabilitation setting, for patients with and without a cognitive
48 impairment^{8,9}. In preparation for a future definitive trial of My Therapy in residential aged care, we
49 aimed to determine the feasibility of My Therapy implementation in the residential aged care setting
50 with respect to acceptability, reach and demand, practicality, integration, limited efficacy testing and
51 adaptations.

52 Methods:

53 The study received multi-site approval from the Alfred Health Human Research Ethics Committee (ID:
54 69610) as well as site specific approval from Eastern Health (ID S21-004-69610). As recommended by
55 Lancaster and Thabane ¹⁰ this feasibility study has been reported according to the CONSORT
56 statement: extension for pilot randomised and feasibility studies ¹¹.

57 *Setting*

58 The study setting was one wing (30 beds) of a 90-bed metropolitan residential aged care facility,
59 attached to a health service, in Victoria, Australia. The 30-bed wing had existing allied health staffing
60 of 0.05 FTE of occupational therapy and 0.4 FTE of physiotherapy. In addition, there was one enrolled
61 nurse or personal care attendant per seven residents during the day.

62 *Participants*

63 Included participants were residents in the designated general residential care wing of the aged care
64 facility. Residents were excluded if they were receiving palliative care. Opt-out consent was used,
65 with each resident, and their family, contacted by a member of the research team and given a full
66 explanation of the study, followed by the option to opt-out. Written informed consent was required
67 for staff focus group and resident survey participation. This observational study did not include
68 randomisation, concealed allocation, or blinding.

69 *Intervention*

70 The original My Therapy program has been previously detailed ¹². My Therapy is based on four
71 principles, (i) the My Therapy program is provided to the participant in writing, (ii) there is a
72 feedback mechanism between the participant and the therapist (e.g., a tick sheet for exercise
73 completion), (iii) the My Therapy program is documented in the medical record, and (iv) the My
74 Therapy program is reviewed regularly. A summary of the original My Therapy program designed for

75 the inpatient rehabilitation setting, and the a priori planned adaptations for the residential aged care
76 setting, are in Table 1, with the My Therapy description based on the TIDieR checklist¹³.

77 *Outcome measures*

78 To determine whether My Therapy for residents in residential aged care meets their needs, the
79 feasibility framework developed by Bowen, Kreuter¹⁴ was used to guide the collection of feasibility
80 outcomes. These outcomes included: (1) **Acceptability** of My Therapy measured by staff and
81 resident reaction to the program; (2) **Reach and demand** for the program measured by resident
82 uptake of My Therapy; (3) **Practicality** of implementing My Therapy in residential aged care with
83 limited allied health resources; (4) **Integration** into the current residential aged care system,
84 including the cost of implementation; (5) **Limited efficacy testing** based on changes to physical
85 function as measured by the DeMorton Mobility Index (DEMMI)¹⁵ and adverse events (e.g., falls), as
86 well as (6) **Adaptations** to meet the needs of aged care residents and staff, that are in addition to
87 the a priori adaptations described in Table 1.

88 *Data collection*

89 Multiple strategies for data collection were employed to address the outcome measures and these
90 were collected between week 1 and week 6 of the 6-week observational study (Table 2). The medical
91 record audit involved a review of each participant's medical record in Week 1 to collect the baseline
92 routinely collected resident characteristic data reported in aged care such as cognition (noting that in
93 this study cognition was reported as present if the treating team documented a cognitive impairment
94 in the resident's medical record, regardless of the tool used to assess this), behaviour (via the
95 Behaviour resource utilisation assessment (BRUA) and Australia-Modified Karnofsky performance
96 status (AKPS)), mobility (via the DEMMI¹⁵) and performance in activities of daily living (via the
97 Resource Utilisation Group: Activities of Daily Living (RUG-ADL))^{16, 17}. The medical record was
98 accessed again in Week 6 to access the follow up DEMMI mobility score (*limited efficacy testing*).

99 The wing audit involved a face to face meeting with the therapy team to determine how many
100 participants had been involved in an initial goal setting meeting with the allied health team (*reach of*
101 *the program*) and how many were provided with a My Therapy program (*demand for the program*).
102 The staff focus groups were conducted in Week 5 and were facilitated by two members of the
103 research team (KL and NB) (*focus groups explored feasibility domains – see Appendix 1*). Based on a
104 sample of convenience, paper-based surveys were provided to select residents in Week 5, with the
105 option to complete the survey in writing, or verbally with a member of the research team (*surveys*
106 *explored program acceptability in aged care – see Appendix 2*). For residents who completed the
107 survey, their My Therapy program was reviewed in detail (*to report on the type and number of*
108 *exercises, number of repetitions, and adaptations for aged care*). The cost of My Therapy
109 implementation was reported via a Week 6 audit, which involved a member of the research team
110 (KL) gaining information from the therapy team regarding My Therapy costs and the staff resources
111 required to support the program (*integration within current aged care resources*).

112 *Analysis*

113 The results have been presented under each domain of feasibility. Binary and categorical data has
114 been presented as a number and as a percentage, and continuous data has been presented as a
115 mean and standard deviation (SD). Two members of the research team independently read the staff
116 focus group transcripts (KL, CE) and applied a directed content analysis approach¹⁸. This approach
117 involves deductively coding qualitative data according to a pre-determined framework, in this case
118 the feasibility domains of acceptability, reach and demand, practicality, integration and
119 adaptations¹⁴. The two researchers coded the qualitative data independently and then refined their
120 coding based on consensus.

121 Results:

122 Over six-weeks, 26 residents were eligible and were included in the study, with the remaining four
123 beds on the wing either vacant (n=2) or converted to palliative care beds (n=2). Resident
124 characteristics are presented in Table 3 as a total cohort, and as cohorts who did and did not
125 participate in My Therapy. Regarding staff participants, there was one occupational therapist, four
126 physiotherapists, one allied health assistant and one physiotherapy student involved in My Therapy
127 program implementation. Two staff focus groups were conducted for an average of 45 minutes
128 (combined n=5 participants). Staff participant characteristics are presented in Table 4.

129

130 (1) **Acceptability** of My Therapy measured by staff and resident reaction to the program

131 Information about the acceptability of My Therapy was collected via resident surveys (=5
132 participants) and the staff focus groups (n=5 participants), with both data sources reporting a
133 favourable reaction to introducing My Therapy into aged care, see Text Box 1.

134

135 Text Box 1: Patient Survey and Staff Focus Group – Acceptability

136 Patient Survey

137 All residents (n=5/5) reported that the program was acceptable in aged care. Residents indicated that
138 the factors that made it easy to participate in My Therapy were the use of simple drawings and
139 explanations and having the support of family; and the factors that made it hard to participate in My
140 Therapy were remembering to complete the program, difficult exercises, lack of motivation, and a
141 visual impairment. To make the program more acceptable in residential aged care, residents reported
142 the programs should have less words, families should be involved, there should be more prompts

143 from the staff to complete the program, as well as more room for “ticks” on the chart (i.e., to allow
144 for program completion more than once per day). In closed survey questions, two of the five
145 residents reported feelings of empowerment associated with program participation, and two of the
146 five residents reported being involved in the decision making process to develop the program, e.g.,
147 goal setting.

148 One resident reported he *“loved doing My Therapy... Helps with walking”*, that he completed his My
149 Therapy program every day, and that it takes about 15 minutes (Resident 1, Male). Another resident
150 reported *“I just want to feel good... want to be able to do things”* and that *“there are things that I*
151 *can’t do any more, but there are things that I can do, and My Therapy [participation] feels like I’m*
152 *doing something”* (Resident 3, Female). Another resident reported wanting to complete self-care
153 grooming tasks (such as putting on make-up) as part of her My Therapy program, however it was
154 difficult to isolate these tasks from the general morning care duties. This resident stated *“The*
155 *(exercises) are probably doing me good, but I don’t feel it”* and that while she had not done the
156 make-up tasks in the morning due to care staff completing the activity for her, she had *“started doing*
157 *it later in the day now [the make-up] is in reach”*, noting the allied health team had set up a make-up
158 station in her room to support independent self-grooming.

159 Staff Focus Group

160 Staff were keen to introduce a program that would enable residents to become more actively
161 involved in rehabilitation self-management, noting that rehabilitation was often a challenge in
162 residential aged care settings. Staff also noted that My Therapy assisted with implementing a new
163 workforce guideline (that is the My Therapy guidelines) relating to exercise prescription in residential
164 aged care.

165 *"My initial reaction to it was great. This sounds perfect because historically [residential aged care] is*
166 *seen as a very passive sort of place, and I don't think that everyone who is living there, that's what*
167 *they necessarily want." (P5)*

168 *"I think it really helped our team. We wanted to increase the amount of exercise residents in the*
169 *facility were doing.... as a project that came out of the world falls guidelines that everyone should*
170 *have as much exercise... and an individualised program where feasible." (P5)*

171 However, one staff member did report some apprehension initially in relation to putting too much
172 responsibility on residents for their own health care.

173 *"One thing I was a little bit apprehensive about was, sometimes self-management programs can be a*
174 *way of putting the responsibility on the resident or the patient. And then if things go wrong, it's their*
175 *fault, not ours, because they didn't implement it properly. And I saw that as a potential danger of*
176 *this." (P5)*

177 Staff spoke about both residents and families reacting positively to My Therapy. Residents reportedly
178 appreciated being more involved in completing their activities of daily living, and families were
179 perceived to have been given a sense of purpose when they visited.

180 *"She was very much on board to be doing a couple of things every day, increasing her movements*
181 *and doing her own makeup, brushing her own hair. She was frustrated by having the nurses do all*
182 *those things for her." (P5)*

183 *"It gives the family a sense of purpose, apart from just the emotional bonding. And that's really good*
184 *for their motivation even just to come more often.... So it's almost like they're coming together in an*
185 *activity that they both find meaningful." (P3)*

186

187 (2) **Reach and demand** for the rehabilitation program measured by resident My Therapy uptake

188 Via initial My Therapy discussions between the resident and the therapists, to determine goals and
189 resident preferences, My Therapy reached 26 residents (n=26/26, 100% *program reach*), with 15
190 residents subsequently receiving a rehabilitation program (n=15/26, 58% *program demand*) noting
191 the remaining 11 residents didn't participate due to resident preference or safety issues (n=11/26,
192 42%). The residents who did (n=15) and did not (n=11) participate in a My Therapy program were
193 similar at baseline, including similar for a cognitive impairment, however they differed with the
194 baseline DEMMI score which was observed to be higher for residents who did participate in a My
195 Therapy program, indicative of a higher level of independent mobility (Table 3). In addition, in the
196 focus groups (n=5 participants) staff reacted favourably to the reach achieved by My Therapy, see
197 Text Box 2.

198

199 Text Box 2: Staff Focus Group – Reach and Demand

200 Staff Focus Group

201 It was evident from the staff focus groups that there was demand for My Therapy in this setting. Staff
202 reported that during usual care there were few residents that had access to either a short term, or
203 long term, rehabilitation program with the allied health team, due to scarce allied health resources
204 and competing allied health staff demands. Staff reported that participating in the My Therapy pilot
205 study gave them the motivation to introduce the rehabilitation exercise programs to the residents.
206 Others spoke about the program providing a framework for implementation, which helped with their
207 clinical reasoning.

208 *“the exercise programs ...had fallen to the wayside a little bit.... But it's something that we've always*
209 *been saying, once we get on top of everything, we're gonna get to do this. And I think My Therapy*
210 *just give gave us a little kick to get some of that stuff done.” (P4)*

211 *“I think we definitely want to continue it. It's been really good to have a framework, ...exercises that*
212 *are a bit more relevant. And also, to just help sort out our thinking in terms of prioritising the*
213 *residents and where physio fits in.” (P1)*

214 Some residents appearing to forget they had been given programs. However, family were often keen
215 to be involved and would assist residents to complete their exercises.

216 *“And there was another person. Had family who [would] come and see her a few times a week and*
217 *they were very keen to come and do the program with her.” (P5)*

218

219 An in-depth review of four resident My Therapy programs found that one program had four
220 exercises, two programs had six exercises and one program had eight exercises (24 exercises
221 prescribed in total across four residents), with the aim of completing the program once per day.
222 Eighteen were seated exercises focused on arm and leg strength, five exercises were self-care
223 grooming tasks for example brushing hair and applying make-up, and one involved standing.

224

225 *(3) **Practicality** of implementing My Therapy in aged care when allied health resources are*
226 *limited*

227 There were no adverse events (e.g., falls) associated with resident participation in My Therapy. The
228 medical record audit demonstrated that it was practical to report My Therapy participation in the
229 residents medical record. The wing audit demonstrated that it was practical to implement My

230 Therapy to all suitable residents over a 3-week period, alongside usual care allied health tasks such
231 as pressure area care, mobility reviews post fall, and the regular 3-monthly review of the residents'
232 care plans. In addition, in the focus groups (n=5 participants) staff reacted favourably to the
233 practicality of My Therapy in their service, see Text Box 3.

234

235 Text Box 3: Staff Focus Group – Practicality

236 Staff Focus Group

237 Time was a factor raised in the focus groups, particularly given the complexity of goal setting, time
238 needed to develop and refine My Therapy programs, and supervision required. For example, time
239 was required to set up person-centred goals:

240 *"I would say that time, time is really important. So time at an individual level, to make that program*
241 *individualised, you need time with the resident, and to collaborate with them."* (P2)

242 The availability of staff to review My Therapy programs was also limited by time:

243 *"...time was something that was, was challenging because weekly reviews aren't really something*
244 *that often happen unless there's like an acute injury or something like that in this setting."* (P5)

245 Lack of time for nursing and care staff was also seen as a risk when it came to providing a supportive
246 environment for residents to exercise or perform activities of daily living slowly but more
247 independently:

248 *"And they certainly don't mean it, but they potentially could undermine some of the My Therapy*
249 *programs that residents are completing, because they don't understand the purpose behind it. So, I*
250 *think that's a time thing as well, to the nursing staff, to understand the purpose behind My Therapy."*

251 (P2)

252 Nevertheless, participants reflected on the potential for My Therapy to be a mechanism to help
253 better direct allied health therapy time and shift the focus to include rehabilitation. Physiotherapists
254 mentioned, for example, that going through the process of collaborative goal setting helped
255 determine “*who should we be actually spending that extra time with?*” In addition, the occupational
256 therapist noted:

257 “... you just wonder if, if we did have the time to set up with, with residents and really great engaging
258 My Therapy programs, then are they are going to maintain their health and well being and
259 potentially, you know, avoid those complications that I feel like I'm band aiding through an equipment
260 perspective down the track.” (P2)

261 The role of the allied health assistant in supporting My Therapy programs was seen as beneficial by
262 staff members, given most residents required supervision: “*having programs for people that can be
263 done with an [allied health assistant], I think, is the most appropriate*”. (P4)

264

265 (4) **Integration** into the current aged care systems

266 For the cost of implementation analysis, it is noted that during the study, the site-co-ordinator was
267 present two days per week; one day per week was to oversee all research requirements, and one day
268 per week was to support My Therapy implementation. Direct costs for implementing My Therapy
269 included a small budget for exercise materials, as well as the cost of the research site co-ordinator
270 who supported My Therapy implementation, which included staff education and supporting the
271 allied health staff to develop the individual resident My Therapy programs. Indirect costs included
272 education sessions for the allied health and nursing team, as well as up to 60 minutes per resident
273 who participated in the My Therapy program (for the initial discussions, joint goal-setting sessions as
274 well as developing and delivering the program to the resident) and 30 minutes per resident who did
275 not participate in the My Therapy program (for just the initial discussions). Table 5 outlines the costs,

276 with a total cost of \$6,491 over the six weeks, equating to \$250 per resident, or \$6 per resident per
277 day. In addition, in the focus groups (n=5 participants) staff reacted favourably to the integration of
278 My Therapy in their service, see Text Box 4.

279

280 Text Box 4: Staff Focus Group – Integration

281 Staff Focus Group

282 Participants in the staff focus groups noted the benefits of interprofessional practice for goal setting
283 and program setup, although were mindful that this may be difficult at other residential aged care
284 facilities, particularly those employing external allied health contractors. For example,
285 physiotherapists reported collaboration with the occupational therapist was particularly helpful:

286 *“...to actually look at both, you know, sort of their, their whole being together. So in terms of their*
287 *mobility, but also what does that actually look like in their functional activities that they want to do?*
288 *... So then we could work together to actually see how that looked.” (P1)*

289 It was reported that integrating My Therapy with existing workflows would require additional staffing
290 for occupational therapy. For physiotherapy, aligning reviews of the My Therapy program with the
291 timing of care plan reviews – every three months – was reported as a possible way to integrate My
292 Therapy into usual care. Some residents would reportedly require more regular review, but this was
293 already the case for some residents:

294 *“...we do ... three monthly care plans... And depending on how many people were on My Therapy, I*
295 *think that's where it would end up falling between one month to three months, because I feel like one*
296 *month is what I would like. But I feel like three months would be a lot more realistic ... If the goal is*
297 *more fluid, and he's likely to... achieve it in a shorter period of time, and ... their goal is going to*
298 *change, then I think their review needs to happen a lot quicker.” (P1)*

299 Staff participants suggested commencing My Therapy would be effective at the beginning of a
300 resident's admission. Reasoning was twofold – first, at that point in time, residents may be less
301 institutionalised and may find it easier to articulate goals focusing on rehabilitation self-management
302 and independence. Second, families are more engaged at this time, and may be keen to continue
303 supporting a My Therapy program.

304 *"I think if we can sort of get them at the door, say, well, what do you want to actually do, and get the*
305 *families involved at that time when families are quite enthusiastic, wanting to, you know, be involved,*
306 *to sort of give them all of them options of how to even make the visits more meaningful and things*
307 *like that. And right from the start, whereas I think a lot of people sort of visit initially and then sort of*
308 *start to almost peter off because they don't know what to do when they visit, whereas I feel like that's*
309 *actually another way of sort of increasing their wellbeing, gives the families purpose."* (P1)

310

311 **(5) Limited efficacy testing based on changes to resident function**

312 It was feasible to collect data for efficacy testing, and this was completed via the medical record
313 audit. The DEMMI score at baseline and at follow-up was observed to be higher for the residents
314 who participated in a My Therapy program, compared to those who did not, and changes to DEMMI
315 scores were minimal over 6 weeks (Table 6)

316

317 **(6) Adaptations that are in addition to those planned a priori (as noted in Table 1)**

318 In the focus groups (n=5 participants) staff adaptations that were required to implement My Therapy
319 into their service were identified, see Text Box 5 and Appendix 3.

320

321 Text Box 5: Staff Focus Group – Adaptations

322 Staff Focus Group

323 Staff reported that adaptations were required largely due to the high prevalence of cognitive
324 impairment in this population and the long-term nature of living in residential aged care. Goal setting
325 was perceived to be difficult due to both these factors, but was particularly effective when
326 conducted by a physiotherapist and occupational therapist in partnership with a resident. Staff
327 reported that it took time to develop meaningful, person-centred goals:

328 *“...it's just the way that you get to some of these goals just takes a bit of meandering to work out the
329 best way to approach it.” (P1)*

330 *“You almost have to bring it down to how are you feeling about the strength in your legs? How are
331 you feeling about your walking? Would you like to be doing a bit more walking? Or would you like to
332 be going outside more have more sort of like, direct thing, almost like prompting things to see if we
333 can hone down on what, what would they actually like to do?” (P4)*

334 Cognitive impairment meant most residents did not complete their My Therapy programs
335 independently, needing support from allied health assistants, care staff or family. Some residents
336 were expected to require ongoing support to participate in their programs. For other residents, there
337 was hope they may develop more independence with time, supervision, and practice:

338 *“A number of residents were really keen to do exercise and [were] great doing the exercises with
339 supervision and prompting, but yeah, really needed supervision and prompting, and so we would do
340 it and then we'd get [the allied health assistant] to help go over the program and then we'd go over
341 the program again.” (P4)*

342 *“She's very much a John Farnham, yeah, country music fan. She had a CD player in her room, but no
343 CDs. So we ended up getting a couple of CDs of John Farnham and Kenny Rogers ... so that she's*

344 *associating the exercise with something that she likes and is positive... But we're also hoping that*
345 *over time, it means that even if the nurses just go in and press play, when they're doing something*
346 *else, it'll help [resident name] to be able to then go out and like do my exercises as well... with that*
347 *hope that long term, it might actually mean that she can self-manage a little bit better.” (P2)*

348 Finally, adaptations related to some of the physical or sensory impairments common with ageing. For
349 example, some residents required assistance to get their paper programs out of the folders they
350 were stored in, due to impaired dexterity. All programs were provided in large font sizes, to
351 accommodate visual changes. Some residents were better able to see drawings of exercises rather
352 than photographs, and it was anticipated that photographs of residents exercising may be less
353 confusing than photographs of unknown models.

354 *“That was a good idea to make [the folders] blue. We can continue that probably. Although they're*
355 *hard from a manipulation point of view to actually get out of the folder as well, it's quite fiddly.” (P4)*

356

357 Discussion:

358 This study demonstrated it is feasible to implement the My Therapy rehabilitation self-management
359 program in the residential aged care setting, in preparation for a fully powered definitive trial. This
360 study found that My Therapy was acceptable to residents and staff, and that there was high reach
361 (100%) and moderate demand (58%) with the My Therapy program providing individual allied health
362 interactions focused on rehabilitation and restoration. Importantly, the staff reported that My
363 Therapy improved rehabilitation reach, as usual care saw few residents with access to either a short
364 term, or long term, rehabilitation program. In addition, My Therapy cost AUD\$6 per resident per day,
365 indicating a low-cost intervention when compared to providing daily supervised therapy sessions.

366 Introducing the novel My Therapy rehabilitation program into residential aged care, provides an
367 opportunity to reform allied health services and focus on the areas of importance identified in the
368 Royal Commission into Aged Care Quality and Safety¹, because at present, services often focus on
369 preventing adverse events, such as falls and malnutrition³, compared to other evidence based
370 interventions, such as exercise prescription¹⁹. My Therapy rehabilitation exercises in the current
371 study were predominantly completed in sitting, and there is strong evidence that a seated exercise
372 programs in residential aged care can benefit cognition, strength, depression and quality of life²⁰. For
373 physiotherapy, a recent survey reported that only 22% of residential aged care facilities in Australia
374 provide physiotherapy based rehabilitation or short term restorative care²¹, despite the Australian
375 Aged Care Quality Standards²² and the Royal Commission into Aged Care Quality and Safety¹
376 emphasising restoration and rehabilitation.

377 Being a feasibility study, this study had several limitations, most notable the small study size, limited
378 period of data collection, and the exclusion of other resident measures of function and physical
379 activity, as well as family experience, from the data collection process. In addition, the included
380 residential aged care service was attached to a large metropolitan health service, and therefore
381 generalisability to independent residential aged care services cannot be assumed. Finally, as the staff
382 and resident participants were not blinded. When this feasibility study is combined with previous My
383 Therapy research (inpatient rehabilitation setting)^{8, 9, 12, 23, 24}, there is a sound rationale to progress
384 this feasibility study to a definitive trial. Considerations for a definitive trial include the inclusion of a
385 diversity of residential aged care services (e.g., private, psychogeriatric) the inclusion of all streams of
386 allied health, a randomised and blinded design to reduce sources of bias, the inclusion of the family
387 perspective, as well as an extended period of data collection to capture the impact on resident
388 function, independence and quality of life.

389 Conclusion: My Therapy has the potential to improve the rehabilitation reach of allied health services
390 in residential aged care. While introducing this low-cost intervention is feasible, adaptations were

391 required for successful implementation due to scarce allied health resources and the complexity of
392 the goal setting process with the residents.

393

394 Table 1: Description of the original My Therapy program designed for the inpatient rehabilitation
 395 setting and the My Therapy program adapted for the aged care setting (noting the aged care setting
 396 adaptations in this table were identified prior to the study commencing)

	Original context: My Therapy for Adult Inpatient Rehabilitation (Aged 18+)	New context: My Therapy for Residents in Residential Aged Care (Adults)
Name	My Therapy for Rehabilitation	My Therapy for Aged Care
Why	Increase the dosage of rehabilitation participation	To reform allied health service provision in aged care to (i) empower residents to participate in meaningful, individually co-designed rehabilitation self-management programs, designed to increase daily physical activity and independence through self-practice, and (ii) improve the reach and impact (rehabilitation) of allied health services
What - usual care	During usual care, the treating physiotherapist and occupational therapist set rehabilitation goals on admission, and then provide daily supervised therapy that is often focused on supporting the patient to maximise function and mobility, to support a safe discharge home or to a place of care	During usual care, the treating physiotherapist and occupational therapist assess the resident, and provide guidance to the care team regarding the residents function and mobility and aim to prevent adverse events such as falls and pressure injuries. Care is provided on admission, at the 12-week resident physiotherapy care plan reviews, and as otherwise clinically required
What-intervention	In addition to usual care, patients receive a self-directed therapy program designed to empower them to self-practice therapy exercises and tasks. My Therapy is based on four principles, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) provided in writing, (ii) feedback mechanism between the participant and the therapist (e.g., a tick sheet), (iii) program documented in the medical record, and (iv) program reviewed regularly 	No change
Who provided	Physiotherapist and occupational therapist. In addition, family and other staff play an important role in encouraging	No change

	the patient to complete their My Therapy program	
How	Following a patient-therapist goal setting session, the program is developed using an online exercise platform to present patients with a consistent format for their My Therapy exercise program https://www.physiotherapyexercises.com/	No change
Where	Inpatient rehabilitation	Residential Aged Care
When and how much	The program is provided on admission to inpatient rehabilitation, with the number of exercises and tasks (and the number of times to complete within a day) based on the patient-therapist goal setting session as well as therapist clinical assessment	At a single time, the program is provided to all suitable residents (suitable with respect to safety and personal choice), with the number of exercises and tasks based on the resident-therapist goal setting session as well as therapist clinical assessment
Tailoring	Individually tailored, with many rehabilitation exercises and tasks focused on goals related to returning home following rehabilitation	Individually tailored, with all rehabilitation exercises and tasks focused on the residents self-determined goals that relate to function and activity participation
Modifications	N/A – this is original program	A list of <u>additional</u> modifications has been developed during this study.
How well	During adult inpatient rehabilitation, My Therapy uptake ranged from 68% to 72%	Uptake on a 30-bed residential aged care wing was unknown prior to this study. It has been recorded as an outcome of this study.

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399 Table 2: Strategies for, and timing of, data collection

Data collection strategy (intended sample)	Data collection timing (Weeks 1-6)	Adaptations	Acceptability	Reach and demand	Practicality	Integration	Limited efficacy testing
Medical record audit, including measures of function (n=30)	Week 1 and week 6			✓	✓		✓
Wing audit (completed once)	Week 4			✓	✓		
Staff focus group (n=4)	Week 5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Resident surveys (n=5)	Week 5		✓				
Review of My Therapy programs (n=5)	Week 5			✓			
Cost of My Therapy implementation (completed once)	Week 6					✓	

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402 Table 3: Baseline characteristics of all participants, as well as participants who did, and did not,
 403 participate in My Therapy

	All resident participants (n=26)	Residents who participated in My Therapy (n=15)	Residents who did not participate in My Therapy (n=11)
Age (years), mean (SD)	82.3 (9.1)	83.0 (10.0)	81.3 (8.2)
Gender (female), n (%)	20 (77)	11 (73)	9 (82)
Cognitive impairment documented in the medical record by the treating team Yes, n (%)	21 (81)	13 (87)	8 (73)
AKPS, mean (SD)	53.8 (20.8)	59.3 (19.4)	46.0 (21.2)
BRUA Problem Wandering or Intrusive Behaviour, n (%)			
Extensively	3 (12)	2 (13)	1 (9)
Intermittently	1 (4)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Occasionally	22 (85)	1 (7)	0 (0)
Not applicable*	0 (0)	12 (47)	10 (91)
BRUA Verbally Disruptive or Noisy, n (%)			
Extensively	2 (8)	2 (13)	0 (0)
Intermittently	6 (23)	3 (20)	3 (27)
Occasionally	2 (8)	1 (7)	1 (9)
Not applicable*	16 (62)	9 (60)	7 (64)
BRUA Physically Aggressive or Inappropriate, n (%)			
Extensively	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Intermittently	6 (23)	2 (13)	4 (36)
Occasionally	8 (31)	4 (27)	4 (36)
Not applicable*	12 (46)	9 (60)	3 (27)
BRUA Emotional Dependence, n (%)			
Extensively	8 (31)	4 (27)	4 (36)
Intermittently	6 (23)	4 (27)	2 (18)
Occasionally	8 (31)	5 (33)	3 (27)
Not applicable*	4 (15)	2 (13)	2 (18)

BRUA Danger to Self or Others, n (%)			
Extensively	1 (4)	0 (0)	1 (9)
Intermittently	2 (8)	1 (7)	1 (9)
Occasionally	8 (31)	6 (40)	3 (27)
Not applicable*	14 (54)	8 (53)	6 (55)
RUG-ADL, mean (SD)	12.2 (SD5.9)	10.6 (5.9)	14.4 (5.6)
DEMMI Raw Score, mean (SD)	3.9 (SD 4.8)	4.9 (4.9)	2.5 (4.6)
DEMMI Converted Score, mean (SD) 0-100	18.0 (SD 19.9)	23.1 (19.1)	11.1 (19.7)

404 AKPS, Australian Modified Karnofsky Performance Status; BRUA, Behavioural Resource Utilisation Assessment; RUG-ADL,
405 Resource utilisation Groups - Activities for Daily Living; DEMMI, De Morton Mobility Index; *Does not require monitoring
406 (person has not engaged in the behaviour in the past)

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409 Table 4: Staff characteristics

Characteristics	Staff participants (n=5), n (%)
Age group (years)	
20-29	1 (20)
30-39	4 (80)
Gender (female)	5 (100)
Profession	
Occupational therapy	1 (20)
Physiotherapy	4 (80)
Qualifications	
Student	1 (20)
Bachelor's degree	3 (60)
PhD candidate	1 (20)

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414 Table 5: Cost of implementation to 26 residents over a 6-week period (AUD \$2023/24)

Cost item	Cost per unit	Data source	Number of units	Cost for the item
Exercise materials	Variable	Variable	Variable	\$300
Site co-ordinator time to support My Therapy implementation - Including 1-hour education sessions to allied health staff (x3) and to the nursing workforce (x1)	1-hour of senior allied health time (Grade 4, Year 2) = \$2,409.00 + 25% loading/week (or \$79.24/hour)	https://vahpa.asn.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/AHP-Vic-Public-Sector-Single-Interest-Employers-EA-2021-26.pdf	0.2 FTE x 6-weeks (i.e. 6 days or 48 hours)	48 hours x \$79.24 = \$3,803.68
Employed allied health time for all 26 residents (as all residents engaged in the initial My Therapy discussion)	1-hour of senior allied health time (Grade 3, Year 2) = \$1,992.50 + 25% loading/week (or \$65.54/hour)	https://vahpa.asn.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/AHP-Vic-Public-Sector-Single-Interest-Employers-EA-2021-26.pdf	26 x 30 minutes x 2 allied health staff (OT & physio) = 26 hours	26 hours x \$65.54 = \$1,704.11
Employed allied health time for the 15 residents who subsequently participated in My Therapy (program co-design session)	1-hour of senior allied health time (Grade 3, Year 2) = \$1,992.50 + 25% loading/week (or \$65.54/hour)	https://vahpa.asn.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/AHP-Vic-Public-Sector-Single-Interest-Employers-EA-2021-26.pdf	15 x 30 minutes x 2 allied health staff (OT & physio) = 15 hours	15 hours X \$65.54 = \$983.14
Marketing and communication materials*	In-kind by the organisation – no cost	-	-	-
Total cost to implement My Therapy across 26 residents				\$6,490.94
Cost per residents (= total / 26 residents)				\$249.65
Cost per residents per day (= total / 26 residents / 42 days (6-weeks))				\$5.94

415 Note: Time for allied health and nursing and care staff to participate in My Therapy education sessions was considered in-kind (i.e., within usual duties to attend education sessions).

417 *Marketing or communication materials were considered to be in-kind as this was provided by the aged care facility at no
418 cost to the project.

419

420 Table 6: DEMMI score from baseline to follow-up

DEMMI Converted Score	Residents who did participate in My Therapy (n=15)	Residents who did not participate in My Therapy (n=11)
Baseline, mean (SD)	23.1 (19.1)	11.1 (19.7)
Follow-up, mean (SD)	24.8 (21.1)	10.6 (20.7)
Change score, mean (SD)	1.7 (4.1)	-1.5 (6.9)

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FOCUS GROUP QUESTIONS	
Q1	What does self-management/My Therapy in aged care mean to you / what criteria are important to you?
Q2	Can you tell me about your experience of using My Therapy (or self-management)?
Q3	What sorts of exercises would you like to be able to prescribe as part of a the My Therapy program?
Q4	What are the current gaps in available exercises within the suite on PTX?
Q5	Prior to the implementation of My Therapy, how would you tailor self-management programs for residents? How would you previously have delivered them? Paper or electronic?
Q6	Can you tell me about what makes My Therapy easy to deliver to your residents (enablers)?
Q7	What made My Therapy hard to deliver to your residents (barriers)?
Q8	Tell me about what you think about including My Therapy in your residents’ overall aged care program?
Q9	What are your thoughts on this statement “it is always appropriate to prescribe My Therapy”? Under what circumstances is it not appropriate?
Q10	How do you feel you can deliver My Therapy with those residents who are cognitively impaired? What are the perceived (or experienced) barriers to delivering My Therapy with residents with cognitive impairment? What are some strategies that may support effective participation of people with cognitive impairment in the My Therapy program? What do you think about the use of photo guides and visual tools to guide My Therapy program delivery for those with a cognitive impairment?
Q11	What are some of the problems you are aware of about getting the dosage of therapy right for the My Therapy Program? What solutions are you aware of that have helped staff in getting the dosage of therapy right for the My Therapy Program?
Q12	What are your thoughts on your time availability to prescribe and modify the My Therapy program?
Q13	How are Allied Health Assistants involved with My Therapy currently? How do you think Allied Health Assistants can be involved in My Therapy in the future?
Q14	What could make My Therapy better? What could we change?
Q15	What concerns do you have about My Therapy?
Q16	Explain how, if at all, My Therapy changed your behaviour towards self-management in aged care/ilatation?
Q17	What do you feel could support the continued implementation of My Therapy after the site co-ordinators finish in their roles?
Q18	How would you describe your residents My Therapy Journey?
Q20	What do you think are some of the strategies to maximally involve residents in developing their My Therapy Program?
Q21	Do you have anything else to add about My Therapy?

Process Evaluation: Patient Survey (My Therapy)

Record ID _____

Please complete this survey on the last day of your 7-day activity log.

When answering these questions, please consider the activities recommended by your occupational therapist or physiotherapist outside of supervised therapy sessions. You may know this program as 'My Therapy'.

Date survey completed: _____

Did you receive a My Therapy program? Yes
 No

If yes, please complete the rest of the questions.

If no, thank you for your time. No need to complete any more questions.

What made My Therapy easy to complete (enablers)?

For example, clear instructions, tasks and exercises set at the right level, tasks and exercises that were meaningful for you, feeling in control of your health, staff and family encouragement.

What made My Therapy hard to complete (barriers)?

For example, the program took too long to complete, the exercises were too hard, you didn't understand the instructions, no dedicated space for exercises, felt alone, needed more encouragement.

What could make My Therapy better? What would you change?

Would you like a copy of the My Therapy program once you finish your rehabilitation? Yes
 No

To what extent does REHABILITATION (in general) give you feelings of empowerment (becoming stronger and more confident with your rehabilitation)?

Not at all To a great extent

=====

(Place a mark on the scale above)

To what extent does MY THERAPY (self-management exercises) give you feelings of empowerment (becoming stronger and more confident with your rehabilitation)?

Not at all To a great extent

=====

(Place a mark on the scale above)

To what extent does REHABILITATION (in general) enable you to self-manage your rehabilitation journey (or part thereof)?

Not at all To a great extent

(Place a mark on the scale above)

To what extent does MY THERAPY (self-management exercises) enable you to self-manage your rehabilitation journey (or part thereof)?

Not at all To a great extent

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Do you think that most people in rehabilitation should be completing a self-management program (e.g. like My Therapy)?

Yes
 No
 Unsure

Was your MY THERAPY program too easy, about right or too hard?

Too easy
 About right
 Too hard

To what extent have you been involved in decision-making about your My Therapy program (for example, setting goals, having a say in the exercises)?

Not at all To a great extent

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Do you want to make any other comments about My Therapy?

431 **APPENDIX 3 - Adaptions, in addition to the a priori adaptations detailed in Table 2**

- 432 • In residential aged care, due to low allied health staffing levels and the complex nature
433 of goal setting for this population, My Therapy programs were gradually implemented to
434 all suitable residents over a 3-week period. *In rehabilitation My Therapy was*
435 *implemented over a 1-week period.*
- 436 • In residential aged care, due to low allied health staffing levels, staff recommended that
437 therapist review of the My Therapy program is every 12-weeks, (aligned with the current
438 time frame for physiotherapy care plan reviews) or more often as clinically indicated. *In*
439 *rehabilitation, My Therapy was reviewed weekly, or more often as clinically indicated.*
- 440 • In residential aged care, due to the My Therapy focus on the residents' goals, programs
441 were co-designed between the resident and the therapist with **equal focus** on increasing
442 physical activity and increasing independence through self-practice. *In rehabilitation,*
443 *there was a strong focus on increasing the dose of therapy participation (i.e., physical*
444 *activity).*
- 445 • In residential aged care, individualised programs needed to emphasise activities that
446 were meaningful to the resident, as well as adaptation to written programs to improve
447 comprehension such as increased font size and inclusion of photographs and some
448 required a medium to long term plan to achieve independent practice (with or without
449 the support of family). *In rehabilitation, independent practice was immediately achieved*
450 *by most patients.*

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